

SPEECH COMPRESSION IN SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Abstract

This paper was written to study speech compression as a particularly significant strategy in the field of translation. Among the problems associated with the close attention of researchers in recent years has attracted the question of simultaneous translation and strategies that allow easing the difficult burden of translators. It is necessary to clarify the fact that the task of a professional simultaneous interpreter is to translate speech while preserving the main message that is transmitted by the speaker. Compression is relevant because of the differences in the grammar of the original language and the target language, as well as because of the cultural characteristics of the languages of the world.

Key words: speech compression, simultaneous translation, speech redundancy.

Аннотация

Данная статья была написана для изучения речевой компрессии как особенно значимую стратегию в сфере перевода. Среди проблем, связанных с переводом в последние годы привлекает вопрос о синхронном переводе и о стратегиях, которые позволяют облегчить трудную ношу переводчиков. Нужно уточнить тот факт, что задачей профессионального синхронного переводчика это перевод речи с сохранением главного сообщения, который передается оратором. Компрессия актуальна из за различия в грамматике оригинального языка и языка перевода, а также из за культурных особенностей языков мира.

Ключевые слова: речевая компрессия, синхронный перевод избыточность речи.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola tarjima sohasida muhim strategiya nutqni kompressiyasini o'rganish uchun yozilgan. So'ngi yillarda tadqiqotchilarning diqqat e'tiborini tortgan bu strategiya tarjimonlarning qiyin yukini yengillashtirishga imkon beradi. Professional sinxron tarjimonning vazifasi ma'ruzachi tomonidan uzatiladigan asosiy xabarni saqlagan holda nutqning yetkasib berish ekanligi ma'lum. Kompressiya asl til va tarjima tilining grammatikasidagi farqlar hamda dunyo tillarining madaniy xususiyatlari tufayli dolzarbdir.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq kompressiyasi, sinxron tarjima, nutqda ortiqcha so'zlarning bo'lishi.

Introduction

People who are far from translation activities treat simultaneous interpreters, as well as other translators, with distrust, since translators have the so-called "strength" or the ability to understand what others do not understand. It is among ordinary people that there is an opinion that the translator can synchronize the speaker's text as they please or profitably, namely, add something, keep silent about something or distort it to the detriment of the client. Sadly, it must be admitted that these prejudices are very common. The whole fault is that, according to psychology, people do not want to feel helpless in someone's hands.

The main reason for this opinion is that simultaneous translation is a fairly new and unexplored area of translation. The interest of researchers in simultaneous translation arose quite recently, or rather at the end of the twentieth century. It should be clarified that simultaneous translation is one of the most popular services, as it helps to save time for both students and speakers. Moreover, a simultaneous interpreter is a "dark horse" in the link of translators, which unites and builds cross-cultural and interracial relationships.

Methods

Over time, it became clear that in many areas there is a great need for professional simultaneous translation. Simultaneous interpretation is the type of

translation that is carried out in conditions of time shortage, as well as increased mental tension. It has been proved experimentally that with a detailed sagitated translation from English to Russian in written form, the syllabic value of the text multiplies at best by one and a half, at worst by two times. But with interpretation, where there is no time for thorough editing, the text monotonously increases by more than three times.

This fact can be explained by the fact that these two languages have different constructions since they belong to different language subgroups. For an adequate translation, it is necessary to use the key translation strategies inventively. If the speaker's speech is pronounced in a lively manner, then it is difficult for the translator, and sometimes it is impossible to translate the given speech. In such cases, the simultaneous interpreter has to consciously compress or reduce the volume of the translated text. Of course, he can increase the pace of his translation, but the fact is that if the translator prefers to increase the pace of speech, this directly leads to an increase in the number of errors in translation. According to scientists, the redundancy level of all European languages is about 60-70 percent. Speech compression is possible only if there is really redundancy in speech. If it is present, it is permissible to omit some elements while preserving the meaning of the statement. If it is not there, we can distort the meaning, which is unacceptable. It should be noted that being able to compress and shorten the speaker's text is one of the main skills of a synchronist. This skill is speech compression and it should be considered the main one in simultaneous translation at cross-cultural meetings. Accordingly, influential scientists working on the theory of translation emphasize this aspect. The translator's task is to determine the redundancy of speech and irrelevant information, replace it with a compact form or omit it if it does not change the meaning of the original text.

The fundamental difference between English and other languages is that speech compression can be found at almost all levels. The economy of the text is very noticeable in grammar, in morphology and in the use of lexical synonyms. It is important to note that compression can be considered as a phenomenon specific to modern English. The reason for this lies in the culture of English-speaking peoples. They try to save their time and shorten words or whole sentences.

Results

According to Z.Rasulov¹, there is a special area in our brain that controls the acceptance and understanding of data coming from outside in a "brief" form. This fact can be explained by the fact that compressed information is more accessible to the human "processor". This is where the question of compression is usually raised, that is, about reducing the size of the translation text compared to the original. It is also necessary to take into account the fact that the meaning must be conveyed accurately and without semantic changes. The appropriateness of speech compression during simultaneous translation is determined by the synchronist within a few seconds, since the translator has seconds to interpret the original text with a lag of no more than 1-4 seconds. Moreover, he has to work through the speech he has heard. Experimental data indicate that the speed of 150-200 words per minute is the upper limit. If there are more words, it does not make it possible to translate the text as it should. In addition to the above, intervals must be present in the text of the synchronist, so that he can hear and understand the speech synchronously. G. V. Chernov² in his works found out the content of the text and its reduction by comparing compressed texts obtained as a result of translation with non-compressed texts. As a result, he announced that 30-38% is the number up to which compression can reach.

Discussion

We came to the conclusion that compression is usually used when:

- The speaker is talking so fast that it is not possible to catch up with his pace;
- There are repeated phrases in the text,
- The message has insignificant words;
- The speaker's thought can be compressed using smaller phrases.

Conclusion

It should also be noted that speech compression in translation occurs using a number of techniques. For example, by replacing synonyms or words-phrases close to

¹ Rasulov, Z.I. (2010). The principle of contextual analysis of elliptical sentences (based on the material of the English language). Bulletin of Chelyabinsk State University,(21),91-94

² Chernov G.V. Simultaneous translation: speech compression – a linguistic problem.
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them with shorter words, omitting secondary words that are repeated and the most recent is loud-motley words redundant in a particular situation. These techniques, as usual, are implemented simultaneously with the mechanism of probabilistic forecasting. Speech compression as a strategy in itself is an unexplored phenomenon, it is particularly interesting for modern researchers. This topic is especially relevant these days, as it is becoming popular and in demand and is developing at lightning speed.

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